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other hand, mutations could have occurred in cytoplasmic genes over time, creating divergence among materials of the same cytoplasmic origin.

Regarding the ancestors introduced recently, it is known that CI 9214, like Hill Selection, originated from Rexark in the United States (Sato 1997). Morong Paroc is native to the Philippines, 560 to Liberia, and OS-6 to the Congo (Pérez et al 1992). The ancestor Tox 1525 F₂DW originated from Nigeria. Lung Sheng 1 was the female parent of IRAT10 developed in Côte d'Ivoire, whereas

Dee-geo-woo-gen is native to China.

To reduce the cytoplasmic uniformity of upland rice cultivars for Brazil, crosses involving Pratão and Dourado Precoce and genotypes whose cytoplasmic genes were derived from the two cultivars should be avoided.

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Screening for rice root system and grain yield simultaneously by single-tiller approach

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Breeding for drought tolerance is among the more challenging tasks in rice breeding. Although ample genetic variability has been reported for components associated with drought tolerance and grain yield, combining them favorably has been rather difficult. Thus, the foremost challenge to breeders of this fragile ecosystem is to identify the trait(s) that would confer a grain yield advantage in crops challenged by low-moisture stress, and devise suitable selection strategies, as phenotyping some drought tolerance components involves destructive sampling.

Root system characters are important for drought tolerance in rice. Combining higher grain yield with a deep root system is desirable. In breeding experiments, where each genotype has

a unique genetic constitution, we need to assess root morphology at the vegetative stage (after imposing low-moisture stress or in well-watered conditions) and forward the filial generation. To achieve this, we adopted a single-tiller approach. Annual rice has evolved from perennial wild. A single or a few tillers removed from the mother plant and planted could grow and yield grains. We assessed the performance of replanted tillers and compared these with corresponding characters of undisturbed plants.

Fifteen rice accessions showing a wide array of variation in several phenological and morphological characters were grown in a randomized complete block design in meter-long PVC pipes filled with sandy loam soil as de-

scribed in Shashidhar et al (1999). Twelve replications were laid out in each of the two contrasting moisture regimes. While plants in the well-watered (control) treatment were irrigated throughout the experiment, in the low-moisture stress treatment, irrigation was withheld during 40–65 d after sowing (DAS) (for details, refer to Hemamalini et al 2000). In both moisture regimes, four replications were sampled for roots at three developmental stages, such as 65 DAS, flowering, and maturity. Root sampling consisted of washing away soil and separating out the primary tiller. At each sampling, the primary tiller with about 5 cm of root and shoot was planted in the main field and maintained under well-watered conditions. Correlation between single-tiller regenerated